

Jaundice Awareness: Shedding Light on Liver Health

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ABSTRACT

"Icterus," manifests as a visible yellowing of the skin and mucous membranes, primarily attributed to the excessive accumulation of bilirubin, a bile pigment, within the systemic circulation and tissues. Notably, neonates bear a disproportionate burden, with an estimated 30 million newborns necessitating therapeutic interventions annually to address jaundice-related complications. Epidemiological insights highlight gender disparities, with females exhibiting a heightened susceptibility to hemolytic jaundice, whereas males demonstrate a predilection for hepatocellular jaundice and hepatic carcinoma. Despite its rarity, Crigler-Najjar syndrome epitomizes the diverse clinical spectrum of jaundice. The etiology of jaundice encompasses a multifaceted interplay of various predisposing factors, including chronic alcohol consumption, illicit drug utilization, and occupational exposure to hepatotoxic agents. Diagnostic evaluation entails a systematic approach, encompassing liver function assessments and advanced imaging modalities to delineate the underlying pathophysiological mechanisms. Therapeutic interventions are contingent upon the identified etiology and may entail endoscopic interventions or surgical interventions aimed at alleviating biliary obstructions precipitated by calculi or neoplasms. Recent strides in jaundice management pivot on early disease detection and tailored therapeutic strategies, notably encompassing universal bilirubin screening for neonates and the adoption of evidence-based management protocols advocated by reputable medical bodies. In conclusion, jaundice emerges as a formidable global health challenge necessitating nuanced clinical management approaches. Ongoing research endeavors aim to deepen our understanding of its intricate pathogenesis and refine therapeutic modalities to ameliorate its impact on public health outcomes.

Keywords: Jaundice, Liver disease Management, Types of Jaundice, Pathophysiology, Medical Sciences

INTRODUCTION

Jaundice is also known as "Icterus". Jaundice is not a disease it is a symptom of lot of diseases. The term jaundice comes from the French word "Jaun" which means yellow, because if someone contracts jaundice disease his/her skin, sclera, mucus membrane and whites of the eyes will exhibit yellowish discoloration. Such a condition usually takes place due to excessive accumulation of bile pigments in the blood circulating in the body and body tissues of the infected person (1). World Health Statistics also show that the prevalence of jaundice in adults is rare but in children as many as 80% of the newborn babies are infected during the first week after their birth because of the fact that at this stage of life they neonatal babies are immature and not capable of processing the bilirubin in their bodies. Different research studies show that the occurrence of hemolytic jaundice is common among female and the ratio is approximately 40,000 patient per 100,000 patients of intensive care unit. The ratio of hepatocellular jaundice and hepatic carcinoma is greater as compared to the female population. Crigler-Najjar syndrome is extremely rare with an occurrence of around 1 case per million live births (2).

Hyperbilirubinemia is another risk factor that causes jaundice among individuals. This happens when the liver is over burdened with the process of excessive quantity of bilirubin it starts accumulating in the human body and leads towards jaundice. The liver can easily process the normal quantity of bilirubin i.e. up to 50 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. The liver has the capacity to metabolize and excrete the bilirubin in the form of bile. The bilirubin is produced during the natural breakdown or destruction of the red blood cells therefore they are also regarded as byproducts of the routine natural breakdown of the red blood cells. Jaundice is usually caused when a disruption in the normal production of bilirubin takes place in the human body (3,4).

CLINICAL MANAGEMENT OF JAUNDICE

The sign and symptoms of jaundice include Yellowish discoloration on eyes, skin, hands and of urine. Weakness, Fever, chills, abdominal pain, and flu-like symptoms. Appropriate investigation starts with the history of associated symptoms and risk factors for liver disease. For this we do liver function test to find out type of jaundice. Blood test, US abdomen test, CT scan (for obstructive jaundice) and MRCP (MRI scan of ducts) and endoscopic US (internal visualization). Treatment of jaundice depends upon cause. If the blockage is because of stones patient will require a technique called ERPC and sometimes patients may require PTBD (percutaneous trans hepatic biliary drainage) and surgery (5).

TYPES OF JAUNDICE

In human body the metabolism process of bilirubin takes place in three different phases. The dysfunction in any one or more of these phases can cause jaundice. **Pre-hepatic jaundice:** The rapid and abnormal destruction or breakdown of red blood cells usually causes Pre-Hepatic Jaundice. This kind of Jaundice can generally occur due to hemolysis that prevents the ability of the liver to remove the excess bilirubin from the blood circulating in the human body. Such type of Jaundice occurs due to diseases like Malaria, Thalassemia, Sickle Cell Crisis, disorder in autoimmune system, Spherocytosis, and use of Drugs or intake of other Toxins. **Intra hepatic jaundice:** Intra Hepatic Jaundice is caused due to the malfunctioning of liver or its ability to metabolize and excrete bilirubin from the blood. The Intra Hepatic Phase is divided into three subgroups (Excessive production of bilirubin, Disturbance in the conjugation process and impaired excretory function). Intra Hepatic Jaundice occurs due to diseases like Cirrhosis, Hepatitis, **Gilbert's Syndrome**, **Crigler-Najjar Syndrome**, use of drugs or intake of other toxic substances (6).

POST-HEPATIC JAUNDICE

Post Hepatic Jaundice or **Obstructive Jaundice** occurs in individuals having abnormality that causes interruption (blockage) in the normal drainage of conjugated bilirubin in the form of bile from the liver to the intestines. Post Hepatic Jaundice occurs as a result of diseases such as pancreatitis, abnormality in the structures of the bile duct, presence of gallstones in the bile duct, congenital, cholangitis, parasitic invasion, malformations, pregnancy, cancerous tumors in the stomach, pancreas, gall bladder or bile duct.

NEONATAL JAUNDICE

Such type of Jaundice occurs in newborn babies. Normally newborn babies are born with a sufficient quantity of red blood cells. In such a condition the neonatal may experience the symptoms of jaundice. Usually it is not a cause for concern and recovery normally takes place within a few days time after the birth. In some cases an extremely high level of bilirubin in neonatal blood causes damages to the brain of such neonatals which is also known as Kernicterus that is caused due penetration of bilirubin into the brain tissues of neonatal (7).

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF JAUNDICE

Normal bilirubin metabolism is illustrated in Fig 1. High levels of bilirubin in blood causes jaundice. Bilirubin is normal breakdown product from the haem, and thus is formed from the destruction of red blood cells. Under normal conditions, bilirubin undergoes conjugation within the liver, making it water soluble. It is then excreted through the bile into GI tract, the majority of which is egested in the faeces as urobilinogen and stercobilin (the metabolic breakdown product of urobilinogen). almost 10% of urobilinogen is reabsorbed into the bloodstream and excreted through the kidneys as shown below (8).

CLASSIFICATION AND FEATURES OF JAUNDICE:

Pathophysiology clearly explains that the occurrence of jaundice is due to one or more of the following mechanisms:

- Increased bilirubin production;
- Decreased hepatic uptake;
- Decreased hepatic conjugation and finally;
- Decreased excretion of bilirubin into bile.

A. INCREASED BILIRUBIN PRODUCTION (Haemolytic acholuric or prehepatic jaundice)

This type of jaundice occur as a results of excessive red cell destruction in intra- and extravascular haemolysis or due to ineffective erythropoiesis. The increased release of haemoglobin from too much breakdown of red cells generally leads to overproduction of bilirubin. Hyperbilirubinaemia develops when the capacity of the liver to conjugate a large amount of bilirubin is exceeded. In premature infants, the liver is efficient in enzyme necessary for conjugation whereas the rate of red cell destruction is a bit high. This results in *icterus neonatorum* which is particularly severe in haemolytic disease of the newborn due to isoantibodies (9).

B. DECREASED HEPATIC UPTAKE

The hepatocyte's bilirubin uptake that involves detachment of the pigment from albumin and its binding to cytoplasmic protein, GST or ligand, may be deranged in certain conditions i.e. due to the use of drugs, prolonged malnourishment and sepsis.

C. DECREASED HEPATIC CONJUGATION

The mechanism that involves deranged hepatic conjugation due to defect or deficiency of the enzyme, glucuronosyl transferase is called decreased bilirubin conjugation. This generally occur in certain inherited disorders of the enzyme in an individual (e.g. **Gilbert's syndrome** and **Crigler-Najjar syndrome**), or acquired defects in its activity (e.g. due to drugs, hepatitis, cirrhosis).

However, hepatocellular damage causes deranged excretory capacity of the liver more than its conjugating capacity. The physiologic neonatal jaundice is also partly due to relative deficiency of UDP-glucuronosyl transferase in the neonatal liver and is partly as a result of increased rate of red cell destruction in neonates.

C. DECREASED EXCRETION OF BILIRUBIN INTO BILE

This type of hyperbilirubinaemia is due to failure of the normal amounts of bile to reach the duodenum.

RECENT ADVANCEMENTS IN MANAGEMENT OF JAUNDICE

1. Advances in the clinical assessment strategies used to identify neonates at risk for the development of severe hyperbilirubinemia and bilirubin neurotoxicity, as well as the treatment measures to control hyperbilirubinemia in newborns, continue to be made.

2. More-frequent feedings: Feeding more frequently will provide your baby with more milk and cause more bowel movements, increasing the amount of bilirubin eliminated in your baby's stool. Maintain normal hydration and enteral nutrition of the jaundiced newborn infant is important. This may be achieved by the encouragement of breastfeeding, the provision of additional oral fluids or may require the intravenous administration of fluid (10).

3. Several different pharmacological approaches are used of which the focus of attention in recent years has been on the haem oxygenase inhibitors (metal meso- and protoporphyrins). These are effective inhibitors of bilirubin production and have been shown to significantly reduce peak serum bilirubin levels in several clinical trials, both when used prophylactically and therapeutically (11).

DISCUSSION

Jaundice, scientifically termed "Icterus," stands as a pivotal clinical manifestation indicative of an array of underlying pathological processes rather than a discrete ailment. Etymologically derived from the French word "Jaun," denoting yellow, jaundice manifests as a distinct yellowish pigmentation evident in the skin, sclera, mucous membranes, and ocular tissues owing to the abnormal accumulation of bilirubin, a bile pigment, within the systemic circulation and bodily tissues (12). This pervasive condition exerts a substantial burden on global health, notably affecting neonates, with an annual incidence of approximately 30 million newborns necessitating therapeutic intervention for complications such as prematurity, birth-related cerebral trauma, bacterial sepsis, or jaundice (13).

Epidemiological data underscore a higher prevalence of hemolytic jaundice among the female demographic, with an approximate ratio of 40,000 cases per 100,000 individuals admitted to intensive care units. Moreover, the incidence of hepatocellular jaundice and hepatic carcinoma surpasses that observed in the female population. Notably rare, Crigler-Najjar syndrome epitomizes the diverse spectrum of jaundice, afflicting roughly one case per million live births (14).

Jaundice's multifactorial etiology encompasses an intricate interplay of various predisposing factors, paralleling those implicated in hepatobiliary disorders. Noteworthy contributors include chronic alcohol abuse, illicit substance utilization, and pharmacotherapy fraught with hepatotoxic repercussions, culminating in heightened bilirubin generation and consequent hepatocellular injury, typified by hepatitis A, B, or C viral infections (15).

The genesis of jaundice is intricately linked to biliary ductal obstruction, stemming from diverse pathologies such as cholelithiasis, cholecystitis, gallbladder neoplasms, or pancreatic malignancies. Hyperbilirubinemia, characterized by an overload of bilirubin processing by the hepatic parenchyma, precipitates jaundice via a cascade of metabolic disturbances (16). The clinical management of jaundice necessitates a systematic diagnostic approach, encompassing a spectrum of investigative modalities ranging from liver function assays and serological analyses to advanced imaging techniques, including ultrasonography, computed tomography scans, magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP), tailored to discern the precise etiological underpinning (17). Therapeutic interventions are contingent upon the identified etiology, encompassing minimally invasive endoscopic procedures or surgical interventions to ameliorate biliary obstructions precipitated by calculi or neoplasms.

Jaundice is categorized into three principal types predicated upon its pathophysiological underpinnings: pre-hepatic, intra-hepatic, and post-hepatic cholestasis. Pre-hepatic jaundice ensues from accelerated erythrocyte breakdown, whereas intra-hepatic variants emanate from hepatic parenchymal dysfunction or dysregulated bilirubin metabolism (18). Contemporary strides in jaundice management pivot on early disease detection and tailored therapeutic strategies, particularly in neonates vulnerable to severe hyperbilirubinemia and associated neurological sequelae. Innovations encompass universal pre-discharge bilirubin screening and the implementation of evidence-based management protocols advocated by esteemed medical bodies such as the American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) (19). Furthermore, therapeutic modalities such as intensified feeding regimens and pharmacotherapeutic agents, including hem oxygenase inhibitors, have demonstrated efficacy in mitigating peak serum bilirubin concentrations and ameliorating clinical outcomes, as corroborated by empirical data gleaned from clinical trials (20).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, jaundice, often perceived as a symptom rather than a disease itself, presents a significant health concern worldwide, particularly among newborns. Its multifactorial etiology, including factors such as alcohol consumption, drug use, and industrial chemical exposure, underscores the importance of comprehensive clinical management. Recent advancements in assessment and treatment, such as universal bilirubin screening and pharmacological interventions like haem oxygenase inhibitors, have significantly improved outcomes. However, further research is needed to enhance our understanding of the complex mechanisms underlying jaundice and to develop more targeted and effective therapeutic strategies. Overall, this review highlights the current state of knowledge regarding jaundice and underscores the ongoing efforts to mitigate its impact on global health.

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